

EFFECTS OF COMBINED TREATMENT ON MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF PBO FIBERS AND ITS POLYMER MATRIX COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Poly(p-phenylene benzobisoxazole) (PBO) fibers have been considered as an ideal reinforcing material for advanced composites, owing to its superior tensile strength and modulus, excellent thermal stability, oxidative stability, and fire resistance. However, their performance in reinforcing a polymer matrix so far has been inadequate, which was attributed to the insufficient interfacial bonding between PBO fibers and the polymer matrix. In this paper, γ -ray radiation treatment, poly(phosphoric acid) (PPA) etching treatment and coupling agent treatment were combined to modify surface of PBO fibers. Effects of combined treatment on properties of PBO fibers and its epoxy matrix composites were investigated. Tensile strength of the fibers was evaluated by statistical analysis using the Weibull distribution. Surface morphologies of the fibers were observed by scanning electron microscopy (SEM), and the surface roughness of the treated fibers was increased obviously. Surface wettability of the fibers was characterized by contact angle analysis. The single fiber pullout strength of the treated PBO /epoxy resin microcomposites was as high as 32MPa. The interlaminar shear strength (ILSS) and compressive strength of the PBO/epoxy composites was increased by 26% and 17%, respectively. The results indicated that the combined treatment highly improved the interfacial bonding between the fibers and matrix, and resulted in much higher mechanical properties of the composites.

1 INTRODUCTION

In recent years, PBO fibers have attracted extensive interest of researchers because of their unique physical properties such as superior specific tensile strength, remarkable specific modulus, thermal stability and chemical stability [1-3]. These excellent properties made it popular as reinforcements in the field of advanced composites for aerospace, transportation and bulletproof. However, poor interfacial adhesion between fibers and matrix resulting from smooth surface and intermolecular structure can affect the whole performance of corresponding composites. Therefore, researches on surface treatment of PBO fibers have been proposed, including plasma [4], enzymatic treatment [5], coupling agent [6], chemical oxidation [7], irradiation [8] and combination treatment of several methods [9, 10], and so on.

Compared to individual method, combined treatment of the mentioned methods improved the interface shear strength (IFSS) through different mechanism. So it is a promising method to enhance interfacial adhesion of PBO fibers to resins.

In our previous work, we investigated the influence of plasma modification, γ -ray irradiation, coupling agent, acid treatment and combined treatments on the strength of PBO fiber filament, and investigated its tensile strength through a Weibull analysis. We found that the surface roughness of PBO fibers treated by γ -ray radiation, PPA etching and coupling agent coating in turn increased, with the excellent mechanical properties well retained [11].

In this paper we reported how the combined treatment of γ -ray radiation, PPA etching and coupling agent coating effected on mechanical properties of PBO fibers and its epoxy resin matrix composites. The crystal structure, surface morphologies, surface wettability and chemical structures of the modified PBO fibers were characterized by XRD, SEM, contact angle analysis and FTIR, respectively.

The interfacial property of PBO fibers with epoxy resin matrix was evaluated by IFSS. Moreover, tensile strength, compression strength and ILSS were measured to evaluate the influence of combined treatment on the mechanical properties of the composites. Meanwhile, interface failure mode was determined by SEM images of interface fracture.

2 EXPERIMENT

2.1 Materials

High modulus PBO fibers were purchased from Toyobo Co. Ltd., Japan. The diameter is approximately 11.8 μm . The yarn contains 1000 filaments and the specific line density is 1640 dtex. The fibers were washed by acetone with ultrasonic bath for 24 h then dried in a vacuum oven at 90 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for another 5 h. Silane coupling agent KH-560 (Fig.1) was provided by Nanjing Yudeheng Fine Chemical Co. Ltd., China. Ep648 epoxy resin and E51 epoxy resin were supplied by Shanghai Resin Factory Co., Ltd., China. The PPA solution was prepared from AR grade acid and ethanol with the same volume. The AR grade boron trifluoride ethylamine complex (analytical grade, $\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{NH}_2 \cdot \text{B}_3\text{F}_3$, BTEC) was purchased from Shanghai Sss Reagent Co. Ltd., China. The AR grade diethylenetriamine was purchased from Tianjing Damao chemical reagent Co. Ltd., China.

Figure 1: Molecular formula of KH560

2.2 Combined Treatment Process

First, PBO fibers were subjected to irradiation of ^{60}Co source, with the radiation dose 30 kGry and dose rate 2.4 kGry / h. Then, the samples were soaked in the PPA solutions for 5 min at 40 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. Last, PBO fibers were immersed in ethanol solution with wt 5% KH-560 for 10 min, and dried at the temperature of 120 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 2 h. The treated samples were designated as PBO-CN.

2.3 PBO/EP composites

PBO fibers were impregnated with the epoxy resin system using a wet winding process. The epoxy resin system consisted of Ep648, acetone and BTEC with the weight ratio of 100:100:3. The impregnations were dried at 25 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 4 h in a vacuum oven to vaporize acetone solvent. The composites were prepared by compression molding successively at 90 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 1 h and 170 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 2 h.

2.4 Characterization

Single filament tensile tests were conducted in accordance with ASTM D3379-75, using the Testometric M350 testing device (Testometric Company Ltd., UK) equipped with a 100 cN force cell. The tensile tests were conducted with a cross speed of 5 mm/min using a gauge length of 25 mm, at 65% RH and room temperature. Forty samples were tested for the original fibers and the treated fibers. The crystal structure of the PBO fibers was characterized by X-ray diffract meter (ADVANCED D8, BRUKER Co., German). The surface morphologies of PBO fibers were observed by SEM (Hitachi S4800, Japan). Before SEM experiment, all samples were coated with a vapor deposited thin layer of gold to induce conductivity. The surface functional groups of PBO fibers were analyzed using Nicolet 5700 model FTIR spectrometer (Vctor 33, BRUKER Co., Germany). The surface wetting behavior of the original PBO and the PBO-CT fibers was analyzed from the measured contact angles between the fibers surface and E51 epoxy resin. An OCA20 Micro dynamic contact angle analysis system was used. IFSS was obtained by the single fiber pull-out test equipment (Tohei Sangyo Co Ltd, Japan). To

prepare the specimens, the E51 epoxy resin system was dropped on the PBO fibers uniformly, and the length of the fibers imbedded in epoxy resin was controlled around 1 mm. The hardener was diethylenetriamine. The two components were mixed in the ratio of 100 parts resin to 8 parts hardener by weigh. Then these specimens were cured for 2 h and post cured for 30 min in oven.

All the mechanical tests of PBO/Ep composites were carried out on a computer-controlled universal testing machine (WDW-100, Changchun material testing factory, China) at room temperature. The tensile tests were in accordance with the Chinese standard GB3354-1999. The speed of crosshead was 2 mm/min. The compression tests were carried out conforming to Chinese standard GB/T3856-2005. The speed of crosshead was 1 mm/min. The ILSS tests of the PBO/Ep composites were measured by the three-point, short-beam bending test method, conforming to Chinese standard GB3357-82. The speed of crosshead was 1 mm/min. ILSS of the composites was determined with the span to thickness ratio of 5 and length to thickness ratio of 10. All fracture surfaces were gold coated for 30 sec to reduce the incidence of surface charging in SEM.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Single filament tensile strength

The statistical distribution of tensile strength of the PBO fibers can be described by Weibull distribution [11]. The Weibull cumulative distribution function takes the form:

$$F = 1 - \exp\left(-L\left(\frac{\sigma}{\sigma_0}\right)^\beta\right) \quad (1)$$

The corresponding density function of the Weibull distribution is:

$$f(\sigma) = \frac{dF(\sigma)}{d\sigma} = \beta \frac{L\sigma^{\beta-1}}{\sigma_0^\beta} \exp[-L\left(\frac{\sigma}{\sigma_0}\right)^\beta] \quad (2)$$

The mean value of a Weibull random variable can be expressed as:

$$\bar{\sigma} = \sigma_0 \Gamma\left(1 + \frac{1}{m}\right) \quad (3)$$

Where, Γ represents the gamma function. σ_0 and β are the Weibull scale and shape parameters, respectively, and σ is the stress level at which failure occurs, F is the probability of failure at or below this applied stress level. L is gauge length. β is related to the distribution of flaws. σ_0 is a function of the severity of the flaws.

Table 1 shows the results of single fiber tensile strength tests. Tensile strength of the treated single fiber decreased by 20%. However, β changed little that indicated the treatment did not change the distribution of flaws. That was because PPA treatment worked only at a few nanometers depth on the surface of fibers, and did not damage the fiber body.

Samples	β	σ_0 /GPa	$\bar{\sigma}$ /GPa
PBO	5.185	2.718	5.0941
PBO-CT	5.38	2.173	3.977

Table 1: Weibull parameters of the tested PBO fibers

3.2 Fibers Surface Topography Analysis

As shown in Fig.2, it can be seen that the surface of original PBO fiber is smooth and clean, however, the surface of PBO-CT fiber is rough. Shallow notches and particles were formed on the surface of PBO-CT fibers (Fig. 2). Clearly, the treatment increased the roughness of the fibers surface. It was attributed that the coupling agent of KH-560 was covered on the PBO surface and PPA etched the PBO fiber.

Figure 2: SEM of PBO fibers, (a) PBO, (b) PBO-CT

3.3 Crystallinity of PBO Fibers

X-ray diffraction intensity profiles for untreated PBO and treated PBO fibers are shown in Fig. 3. Table 2 shows the crystallinity of PBO fibers and PBO-CT fibers. The equatorial diffraction patterns revealed the intermolecular regularity between neighboring polymer chains. The average crystal size of (200) plane was calculated through Scherer's formula. The treated PBO fibers showed slightly bigger average crystal size than that of untreated PBO fibers. The average crystal sizes of PBO fibers and PBO-CT fibers were 8.4 and 8.8 nm, respectively. This showed molecular chains cross-linked induced by the gamma bombardment result in the increase of the intermolecular regularity. After combined treatment, the crystallinity of PBO-CT was increased to 92.52 %. It can be ascribed that the crystalline structure of PBO fibers could be promoted under γ -ray radiation, owing to the cross-linked PBO chains. Moreover, amorphous PBO dissolved easier than crystal PBO in the PPA solution. Finally, the crystallinity of PBO fibers was increased slightly.

Figure 3: XRD of different PBO fibers

3.4 FTIR Analysis

Fig. 4 shows the FTIR results of PBO fibers and PBO-CT fibers. In Fig. 4, a new absorption peak appeared at 2096 cm^{-1} which was stretching vibration of $-\text{CN}$ group, indicating the fact that PBO fiber surface was changed after combined treatment and formed cyanoguanidine group, which was thought to be the reason of the increasing of fibers surface polarity, the decreasing of contact angle, the improvement of adhesion between fibers with epoxy, and the IFSS. The result was consistent with the following contact angle analysis and the IFSS results.

Figure 4: FTIR spectra of different PBO fibers

3.5 Contact Angles between PBO Fibers and epoxy resin

The contact angles between PBO fibers and E51 epoxy resin are shown in Figure 5. It is well known that fibers wettability is the characterization of surface free energy. Combined treatment decreased the contact angle from 113 ° to 74 °, indicating that the treatment improved surface free energy of PBO fibers. The improvement of the surface free energy was mainly attributed to the significant increase of the polar component. As the Cyanoguanidine group in the fiber and the epoxy group in KH560 had strong affinity to epoxy resin, good wetting and adhesion properties obtained.

Figure 5: Contact Angles of PBO fibers (a) and PBO-CT fibers (b)

3.6 IFSS Test

The influence of combined treatment on IFSS between PBO fibers and the epoxy is shown in Table 3. IFSS between PBO fibers and the epoxy were improved significantly after combined treatment. The IFSS was 27.5 MPa before combined treatment, and increased to 31.8 MPa after combined treatment.

The improvement could be due to a micron-sized interfacial region formed by the KH560 chains and polar groups on PBO fibers. The coupling reactions between the groups on KH560 and PBO fiber with epoxy resin matrix thereby resulted in a tougher and stiffer interfacial region. The other reason could be due to a fact that the higher roughness of the PBO fiber surface, the better mechanical interlocking between the fiber and matrix.

	PBO	PBO-CT
IFSS/MPa	27.5	31.8

Table 3: IFSS of PBO and PBO-CT fibers between epoxy resin

3.7 Mechanical properties of composites and fracture mechanism

The measured tensile strength, compression strength and interlaminar shear strength of the composites are shown in Table 4. Due to decreasing of the tensile strength of the treated single

filament, the tensile strength of PBO-CT/Ep composites decreased by 8 %. The ILSS increased by 26 % to 43 MPa and compression strength of PBO-CT/Ep composites was improved by 17 % to 168 MPa. The result indicated that the combined treatment can improve the interfacial adhesion between PBO fibers and the epoxy resin matrix significantly.

Samples	Tensile strength /MPa	Compression strength /MPa	ILSS/MPa
PBO/Ep	3072	144	34.38
PBO-CT/Ep	2894	168	42.98

Table 4: Mechanical properties of the composites

Figure 6: Photographic image of the PBO/Ep composites tensile fracture surface (a), Photographic image of the PBO-CT/Ep composites tensile fracture surface (b), SEM image of the PBO/Ep composites tensile fracture surface(c), SEM image of the PBO-CT /Ep composites tensile fracture surface (d), Photographic image of the PBO/Ep composites compression fracture surface (e), Photographic image of the PBO-CT/Ep composites compression fracture surface (f), SEM image of the PBO /Ep composites compression fracture surface(g), SEM image of the PBO-CT/Ep composites compression fracture surface(h)

Macroscopic images of tensile failure samples are shown in Fig. 6(a) and (b). These macrographs show that the fibers adhesion, which may be related to the amount of resin still bonded to fibers after rupture, highly varies in the treated and untreated samples. In Fig. 6(a), the PBO fibers composites exhibited failure accompanied with matrix debonding, In Fig. 6(b), the PBO fibers composites exhibited failure accompanied with matrix cracking. The result can be considered as the evidence for efficient load transfer between the epoxy matrix and the PBO-CT fibers. SEM images of tensile fracture surfaces of the untreated and treated composites are shown in Fig. 6(c), (d). It is found that the fibers are smooth with low amount of resin adhered to surface of the untreated specimen. This means that the interfacial adhesion between the PBO fibers and the epoxy resin was quite poor. The interfacial adhesion was improved considerably as shown in Fig. 6(d). It can be seen that the gaps between the PBO fibers and the epoxy resin are very small. The bonding strength between the fibers and the matrix was enhanced. The uniaxial compression failure mode of the composites was mainly the 45 °shear failure mode (Fig. 6 (e)). Some samples of treated composites failure mode yielded (Fig. 6 (f)). SEM images of compression fracture surface of the untreated and treated composites are shown in Fig. 6(g) and (h). The kink bands on PBO and PBO-CT fiber surface were induced by axial compression. The untreated PBO fibers were debonding and microbuckling, while the PBO-CT fibers were broken. This indicated the interface was strong enough to transfer load. That result confirmed that the combined treatment was an effective method to improve the interfacial adhesion between the PBO fibers and the epoxy matrix.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Effects of the process of combined of γ -ray radiation treatment, PPA etching treatment and coupling agent coating on the interfacial adhesion between PBO fibers and epoxy resin were investigated. FTIR provided a proof that the treatment made a new polar functional group formed. Contact angle tests showed that combined treatment improved the wettability of the fibers to the epoxy resin. The IFSS tests showed that the combined treatment could improve the interfacial adhesion in the composites. The reason for the promotion of the interfacial adhesion was due to the increase of the mechanical interlocking and interactions of polar groups with epoxy resin. The tensile strength of the modified PBO/Ep composites decreased by 8%, but the ILSS increased by 26 % to 43 MPa and the compression strength was improved by 17 % to 168 MPa. Composites fracture SEM photographs illustrated that the primary failure mode of the composites changed from interface failure to matrix failure after the combined treatment. All the results indicated that the combined treatment highly improved the interfacial bonding between the fibers and the epoxy matrix, and resulted in the significantly improved mechanical properties of the composites.

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